

Effect of Multimodal Instructional Strategy on Students' Academic Performance in English Grammar in Bayelsa State.

Eke, Regina Akudo¹ & Dr. O. O. Ochuba²

¹Department of Curriculum and Educational Technology
University of Port Harcourt.

²Department of Educational Foundation (Language Arts)
University of Port Harcourt.

ekeregina@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13826297>

Abstract

The study investigates Effect of Multimodal Instructional Strategy on Students' Academic Performance in English Grammar in Yenagoa Local Government, Bayelsa State. This study adopted a Pre-test Post-test quasi-experimental design. Purposive sampling technique was used to get a sample size of 75 students from three secondary schools in Bayelsa State. two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The instrument for data collection was the multimodal instructional package designed by the teacher titled “English language performance test”. The instrument was validated by three subject matter experts and two experts in measurement and evaluation. Pearson Product Moment was used to calculate the reliability of the instruments at 0.81 reliability index. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was used to test the Hypothesis. The result indicated that students taught English grammar using Multimodal instructional strategy performed better (Pretest; $\bar{x} = 42.31$, SD = 5.01, Post-test; $\bar{x} = 67.69$, SD = 4.93, mean gain = 25.38). The mean scores increased significantly from the pretest to the post-test, indicating a positive impact of the Multimodal instructional strategy. The findings also revealed that, female students have higher performance scores in both teaching strategies; 61.04 for Multimodal strategy and 56.75 for Lecture method compared to their male counterparts who scored 58.38 and 57.08, respectively. It is therefore recommended that Teachers should incorporate multimodal instructional strategies when teaching English grammar to enhance student’ performance, due to its effectiveness in improving the learning outcomes. More attention should be paid on the male gender to boost their performance.

Keywords: Multimodal, Academic Performance, Instructional strategy, English Grammar.

Introduction

Grammar is an essential component of teaching and studying languages since it deals with the entire framework and systems of all languages, including English. Since grammar is what gives the English language its structure and meaning, it is very important. Expressions lose their meaning when grammatical rules are broken, which impedes communication. One could consider grammar to be the foundation of the English language. Olufunto (2018) described grammar as the brainstem of every language, and proficiency in it indicates competence. This implies that a proficient grammar user must also be a competent English language user. Teachers’ teaching strategies play

an important role in improving student's academic performance. Performance is measured to determine results and this can be done through several ways depending on the nature of task. It can also be used to find out the strength and weakness of task performed (Ngwu, 2023). By using effective teaching techniques, a teacher can help students comprehend the purpose of learning by guiding them toward achieving set goals. They can also cover topics that range from the known to the unknown and from simple to complex (Kinikanwo-Samuel, 2023). Teaching strategies, according to Onajite (2022), are the intricate methods in which a teacher uses processes, instruments, discipline, tactics, and communications to achieve learning objectives. According to Oden (2015), a teacher's presentation style is just one component of his teaching strategies; other components include the settings in which he gives instructions, assigns homework, oversees group projects, and provides resources to aid in learning. Oden (2015) described teaching strategies as the practice and improvement of presentation that a teacher utilizes to make his lesson more successful and interesting. Because students of the 21st century are digital natives and are being taught by digital immigrants, educators must employ suitable pedagogical approaches to foster creativity and innovation.

The multimodal instructional strategy is a student-centered approach that relies on digital technology to facilitate learning and expects students to actively participate in the process. This approach is evident in the modern teaching and learning environments. In order to accommodate the various ways that people learn, multimodal learning emphasizes the value of including visual aids, auditory signals, hands-on activities, and other sensory experiences in educational settings. The traditional pedagogy of knowledge transmission, which holds that instructors are information representatives, is challenged by multimodal approaches (McKee, 2017).

It encourages a holistic approach to teaching that acknowledges and addresses the individual differences in learning styles. The idea is that individuals may have strengths in one or more modalities, and educators should tailor instruction to accommodate these diverse learning preferences. Multimodal learning proposes that people have preferred ways of processing information, and incorporating multiple modalities can enhance the learning experience. Hence, multimodal learning suggests that individuals have different preferences for learning through various sensory modes, including visual, auditory, kinetic, read/write and tactile channels. Therefore, the study tends to investigate the effect of Multimodal Learning Strategy Secondary School Students Academic Performance in English Grammar.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research is to determine the effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' performance in English Grammar in Yenagoa Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. The specific purpose of the study is to:

1. Ascertain the effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' mean performance scores in English Grammar.
2. Determine the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught English Grammar using Multimodal strategy and Lecture method.

Research Questions

In order to achieve the objectives of this study, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. What is the effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' mean performance scores in English Grammar?
2. To what extent does the mean performance scores of male and female students taught English Grammar using Multimodal strategy and Lecture method.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test post-test performance scores of students taught English Grammar using Multimodal Instructional strategy.

Review of related Literature

The Concept of Multimodal:

There is a need to develop new avenues for teaching and learning using text and multimedia technologies because the scope and limitations of traditional educational techniques, which rely on printed text, are limited. Plastina (2013) contended that multimodal representations of information and content have been made possible by the rapid advancement of technologies. Advocates of multimodal teaching and learning think they have the answers for educating future kids in the classroom. Teachers and students deal with a wide variety of information and data processing mechanisms in the classroom. When many forms of expression—such as text, images, audio, video, and gestures—are combined to convey meaning or information, it's referred to be multimodal. Lesson delivery is made possible by multimodal learning environments in several sensory modes (written, audio, and visual). Differentiating how instructions are presented might make students feel that learning is simpler and focus better, which will enhance learning outcomes. This is especially true for kids who perform less well in school (Sankey, Birch, & Gardiner, 2010). It has also been observed that presenting material in a variety of modes may also encourage students to develop a more versatile approach to their learning.

Some benefits of using visualizations in learning environments, include:

- (1) promoting learning by providing an external representation of the information;
- (2) deeper processing of information; and
- (3) maintaining learner attention by making the information more attractive and motivating, hence making complex information easier to comprehend.

According to Mohammed and Awal-adam (2020), the use of various representations has long been acknowledged as a very effective technique to promote comprehension, especially in computer-based learning environments. For example, a visual representation can frequently solve the communication issue when written words are unable to adequately convey a notion (Mohammed, & Awal-adam 2020). Using audio-enhanced PowerPoint slides as mini-lectures, typically with point form text or images, interactive diagrams with transcripts and voiceovers, video presentations, interactive graphs and forms, audio explanations of concepts, and still images are a few basic examples of multiple representations. In some instances, extra representations of

the information presented in text-based explanations are given via the multimedia elements (visual, audio, and interactive).

The Emergence of Multimodal Learning in Teaching and Learning

The term "emergence multimodal" describes how several communication modalities—like text, graphics, audio, video, and interactive elements—are combined to improve the educational process. This method recognizes that people have different learning preferences and styles, therefore offering a variety of representational options can serve a larger spectrum of learners. The impact of the multimodal revolution on education is one important topic to consider. To develop more dynamic and engaging learning environments, educators are progressively integrating multimedia materials into their lesson plans (Sankey, Birch, & Gardiner, 2010). For instance, instructors may employ virtual reality, simulations, or multimedia presentations in addition to traditional lectures to help students understand difficult subjects and become more engaged. In addition, technology is a major enabler of the multimodal revolution. Teachers now have unparalleled access to a multitude of multimedia resources and chances for collaborative learning thanks to the development of digital tools and platforms. Students can access course materials at any time and from any location through seamless integration of several media formats made possible by online learning management systems (LMS).

Students are encouraged to take part in conversations, work on multimedia projects, and do hands-on activities rather than just passively absorbing material. This enhances their comprehension of the topic matter and develops their ability to think critically and solve problems. The multimodal revolution has consequences for assessment procedures as well. Examinations and essays are examples of traditional means of assessment that might not be able to fairly represent the range of abilities and competences that are acquired through multimodal learning experiences. In order to more correctly measure student learning outcomes, educators are investigating alternate assessment methods, such as multimedia presentations, e-portfolios, and peer assessments. A paradigm change towards more inclusive, participatory, and learner-centered educational approaches is represented by the advent of multimodal learning in teaching and learning. A multimodal literate educator may effectively use technology to create dynamic learning experiences that meet the requirements and preferences of every student by embracing a wide range of communication modalities. Being able to interact appropriately with multimodal texts is necessary for both critically analyzing their contents and creatively creating multimodal artifacts (Jewitt & Kress, 2003).

Improving Teaching and Learning and students' academic performance with Multimodal Strategy:

Madden, (2014) described performance as an activity that serves as a guarantee to a set goal. Performance consists processes and strategies studied within a phenomenon to find out the result gotten within the expected outcome. Good performance is the bases by organizations or individual to decide its efficiency to prevail. The teachers that work at the school have a direct impact on the students' academic success. For both teaching and learning, teachers are indispensable. It should come as no surprise that achieving the desired results in his academic obligations is the definition of a good teacher (Uchefuna, 2011).

In order to improve understanding and memory of information, multimodal tactics in teaching and learning incorporate a variety of sensory modalities, including tactile, kinetic, visual, and aural. A multimodal learning environment enables the presentation of educational materials in several sensory modes, such as written, audio, visual, and so on (Sankey et al., 2010). Undoubtedly, accommodating diverse learning styles is aided by the integration of multimodal techniques into teaching and learning. Individuals learn in a variety of ways, such as kinetic, auditory, and visual. Diverse student preferences can be reached by educators through the use of multimodal techniques. Diagrams and charts, for instance, may be helpful for visual learners, lectures and debates for auditory learners, and hands-on exercises for kinetic learners (Mohammed & Awal-adam, 2020). The various ways that multimodal can enhance teaching and learning are listed below.

❖ **Increasing involvement:**

Using several modalities in instruction raises student involvement. Multimodal techniques can raise student engagement by combining many forms of communication, like group discussions, interactive simulations, and films. Students that are actively involved in their education are likely to pay more attention, contribute more, and learn more efficiently overall.

❖ **Increasing Motivation:**

By offering varied and interactive learning experiences, multimodal strategies can increase students' motivation to learn. When students see the relevance and applicability of what they are learning, they are more likely to stay motivated and actively participate in the learning process.

❖ **Preparation for the Digital Age:**

In today's digital world, being able to navigate and create multimodal content is increasingly important. By integrating multimedia tools and platforms into the curriculum, educators prepare students for success in a technology-driven society.

❖ **Enhancing Retention:**

According to research, using several senses at once may enhance memory retention. Differentiating how information is presented opens up new routes for encoding and retrieval, which helps pupils retain and recall the material at a later time.

❖ **Promoting Critical Thinking:**

Multimodal learning encourages students to analyze information from different perspectives. For instance, when studying a historical event, students might analyze primary sources (visual), listen to accounts from different historians (auditory), and engage in role-playing activities (kinetic), fostering critical thinking skills.

❖ **Supporting Inclusivity and Accessibility:**

Students with impairments and other unique learning styles can be accommodated by multimodal techniques. For instance, students with hearing impairments benefit from transcripts of videos, and students with vision impairments benefit from tactile features. It supports information accessibility and inclusion for students with a range of learning methods.

❖ **Fostering Creativity:**

Multimodal learning environments provide opportunities for students to express themselves creatively. For instance, students might create multimedia presentations, digital stories, or interactive projects, allowing them to demonstrate their understanding in innovative ways.

❖ **Facilitating Real-World Connections:**

Multimodal learning experiences often mirror real-world situations where information is presented through a variety of mediums. By exposing students to diverse communication formats, educators help them to develop skills needed to navigate and succeed in various professional and personal contexts.

❖ **Continuous Improvement:**

Educators can use multimodal strategies to continuously assess and improve their teaching practices. By gathering feedback from students on which modalities are most effective for their learning, educators can tailor their instruction to better meet the needs of their students over time.

Instructional Strategy

Education is the process of learning and teaching in which a teacher presents a lesson on a subject using a variety of strategies or tactics. One of the most crucial issues in education right now is how to present the material to the class so that they may comprehend it quickly, engage with it, and learn more. In his work, Carag (2020) advocated for a number of innovative techniques that would enhance student performance, cater to a variety of learning styles, and enhance the educational process. Akinola (2016) defines a teaching strategy as a plan that outlines the approach teachers will use in order to achieve the intended outcomes. In order to accomplish learning objectives, it concerns with how educators organize and use subject information, instructional aids, and instructional resources. Teaching strategies, pedagogical tools, or techniques employed by educators to impart knowledge in a way that fosters long-term behavior modification—a process known as learning—are all referred to as instructional strategies. Adeyemo (2016) asserts that because the National Policy on Education's high standards for educators are not upheld in the classroom, students' academic performance is impacted by teachers' subject-matter expertise, instructional strategies, and dedication to their positions. Teachers attempt to teach knowledge to their students through their ways.

According to Adeyemo (2016), the instructor has the biggest influence on the learning of the pupils. Over the course of teaching and learning, teachers act as the intermediaries for knowledge, values, and skills. If a teacher has a poor method of instruction, the students they are instructing will not advance academically quickly. Both teachers and students experience less stress when instructional materials are used in the teaching process. Schools are routinely evaluated based on the academic success of their students (Kinikanwo-Samuel, 2023). Consequently, it makes sense to evaluate instructors' effectiveness in terms of their teaching strategies using the findings of their students' standardized tests.

Multimodal Technique:

Bezemer & Kress (2016) define multimodal pedagogies as the manner in which educators can create learning experiences by utilizing a variety of multimodal resources. In order to convey, arrange, and sequence the curricular contents in a multimodal manner, teachers must select effective multimodal resources (Kress & Selander, 2012). Words, pictures, videos, audio, kinetics,

haptic, symbols, and animations are examples of multimodal resources. In order to improve the learning process, multimodal pedagogy combines many communication modalities, including textual, kinetic, auditory, and visual. It recognizes that individuals have diverse learning preferences and styles, and by incorporating various modes of communication, educators can engage learners more effectively and promote deeper understanding.

According to McKee (2017), multimodal pedagogy is a component of the multiliteracies pedagogy framework, which examines the various modes of instruction and learning that are utilized in classrooms and enables teachers and students to combine and integrate these modes to create meaning that is meaningful to them. By utilizing efficient multimodal resources, multimodal pedagogies can expand students' capacity for creativity, critical thinking, and opportunity to explore novel concepts. To effectively accomplish the learning objectives, it is critical to understand the various meaning-making resources and how to use them to create a cohesive and coherent multimodal text (Kress, 2010).

Methodology.

This study adopted a Pre-test Post-test quasi-experimental design. Purposive sampling technique was used to get a sample size of 75 students from two secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Two schools in their intact classes (all the students in the two classes) were used for the study. Intact classes were studied so as not to disrupt the normal academic programme of the schools that participated in this study. One school was assigned to experimental group while one school was assigned to control group using a simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a test developed by the teacher based on the topic taught (English Punctuation Marks), titled English performance test. The English Performance Test (EPT) comprised forty (40) multiple choice questions with options (A-D) selected from the lessons that were taught to the students. The EPT is set to specifically test the students' academic performance in English Language. Prior to the introduction of the treatment, the pre-test was given to ascertain the students' level of knowledge. After the treatment which lasted for four weeks, the test items were reshuffled and administered as post-test. Each correct answers were scored 2.5 marks, hence the test score has a minimum of zero (0) and maximum of hundred (100) scores. To ensure that the instruments measured what it was supposed to measure in terms of wide coverage, accuracy, spellings, language use and to elicit adequate information in terms of objective of the study, research question and hypothesis, the instrument was validated by three subject matter experts and two experts in measurement and evaluation. The corrections and suggestions made by these experts in the context of clarity, ambiguity and the generality of the items were used to modify the research instrument for face and content validity. Pearson Product Moment was used to calculate the reliability of the instruments. The reliability index of 0.81 was obtained and used to determine the reliability of the instrument.

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was used to test the Hypothesis.

Research Questions 1: What is the effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' mean performance scores in English Grammar?

Table 1: The effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' mean performance scores in English Grammar.

Test	N	Mean	Std. D	Mean Gained
Pretest	35	42.31	5.01.	
Post test		67.69	4.93	25.38

The mean scores increased significantly from the pretest to the post-test, indicating a positive impact of the Multimodal instructional strategy. The result indicated that students taught English grammar using Multimodal instructional strategy performed better (Pretest; $\bar{x} = 42.31$, $SD = 5.01$, Post-test; $\bar{x} = 67.69$, $SD = 4.93$, mean gain = 25.38).

However, there's a slight decrease in mean scores from the post-test to the post post-test, suggesting a potential decline in performance over time. The standard deviations provided insights into the variability of scores within each phase.

Research Questions 2. To what extent does the mean performance scores of students taught English Grammar using Multimodal strategy and Lecture method differ based on their gender?

Table 2: Difference in mean performance scores of students taught English Grammar using Multimodal strategy and lecture method based on their gender.

Gender	N	Multi. Mean	LEC. Mean
Male	16	58.38	57.08
Female	19	61.04	56.75

The mean performance scores of male students taught English Grammar using Multimodal strategy and Lecture method are 58.38 and 57.08, respectively. Female students, on the other hand, have mean performance scores of 61.04 for Multimodal strategy and 56.75 for Lecture method. The data suggests that female students have higher performance scores in both teaching methods compared to their male counterparts.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' mean performance scores in English Grammar compare to their pre-test post-test.

Table 4.7: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' mean performance scores in English Grammar compare to their pre-test post-test.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects								
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^b
Corrected Model	149.295 ^a	2	74.647	131.420	.000	.683	262.839	1.000
Intercept	1.019	1	1.019	1.794	.183	.014	1.794	.265

Pre-test Post-test	61.584	1	61.584	108.42 1	.000	.471	108.421	1.000
Multi	72.132	1	72.132	126.99 0	.000	.510	126.990	1.000
Error	69.297	67	.568					
Total	620.000	70						
Corrected Total	218.592	69						

a. R Squared = .683 (Adjusted R Squared = .678) b. Computed using alpha = .05

The above result displays the effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' mean performance scores in English Grammar compare to their pre-test post-test. In the results, both Pre-test Post-test and VAK have observed powers of 1.000, indicating very high confidence in detecting differences. As such a statistically significant effect of treatment, ($F=126, p<.05$). The ANCOVA analysis shows significant differences between the groups (Pre-test Post-test and Multimodal) while controlling for other variables. The effect sizes (Partial Eta Squared) and power values indicate a strong and reliable effect. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected therefore; there is a significant effect of Multimodal Instructional strategy on students' mean performance scores in English Grammar compare to their pre-test post-test.

Discussion and Finding

From the analysis carried out, the findings of research question one showed that students performed better when taught English grammar using multimodal Instructional strategy, as compared to those who were not exposed to multimodal strategy. The mean scores increased significantly from the pretest to the post-test, indicating a positive impact of the Multimodal instructional strategy. The findings of research question two suggests that, on average, female students have higher performance scores in both teaching methods compared to their male counterparts.

Furthermore, the result of hypothesis one showed that there is significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught English grammar using multimodal Instructional strategy from the pretest to the post-test. This finding agrees with previous study by Bawa (2018), who found out that students exposed to multimodal approach performed better than those exposed to conventional teaching method in learning chemistry concepts. This finding is also in agreement with Kuo, Yu, and Hsiao, (2018) who found out that those students who were exposed to multimodal presentation performed better than those who were exposed to blackboard/ marker board presentation.

Conclusion

The study investigated the effect of multimodal instructional strategies on secondary school students' academic performance in English grammar in Yenagoa L.G.A of Bayelsa State. Consequently, the findings of this study showed that students who were exposed to multimodal

instructional strategy demonstrated higher levels of academic performance, in English grammar compared to those who were not.

Based on the outcome of this study, it can be deduced that the use of multimodal instructional strategy in teaching English grammar in secondary schools can lead to improved academic performance among students.

Recommendations.

Based on the findings, it is therefore recommended that Teachers should incorporate multimodal instructional strategies when teaching English grammar to enhance student performance, due to its effectiveness in improving the learning outcomes.

Reference.

- Adeyemo, A. (2016). A Compendium of basic principles and practices of general and special education. Deob International Publishers.
- Akinola. V.O. (2016) Psychological Issues in teaching science subjects: Student Review of the Science Curriculum. London, N R: Corwin.
- Bawa, M. (2018). Effect of Multimodal Instructional Approaches on Students Learning of Chemistry Concepts in Selected Colleges of Education. International Journal of Chemistry Education.
- Bezemer & Kress, (2016) Multimodality, learning and communication: A social semiotic frame.
- Carag E. A. (2020). Pedagogical approaches used by teachers in teaching MAPEH in the Division of Tuguegarao City, Philippines. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation.
- Kinikanwo-samuel, (2023) Effect of Mixed Mode and Collaborative Instructional Strategies on Biology students' performance and Interest in River State.
- Kress & Selander (2012) Multimodal design, learning and cultures of recognition. The internet and higher education.
- Kress, G. (2010) Multimodality: a social semiotic approach to contemporary communication. Abingdon/New York: Routledge.
- Kress, G. and Jewitt, C. (2003) Introduction: Multimodal Literacy. New York: Peter Lang. In C. Jewitt, G. Kress (Eds).
- Kuo, F. O., Yu, P. T., & Hsiao, W. H. (2013). Develop and Evaluate the Effects of Multimodal Presentation System on Elementary ELS Students. The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology.
- Oden. C. (2015). Strategies for improving teaching and learning of business studies in secondary schools in Umuahia Educational Zone, Abia State.
- Olufunto, B. O. (2018). Improving Achievement in English Grammar Among Senior Secondary Students Through Teacher-Student Interaction, Lesson Delivery and Job Satisfaction in Ibadan, Nigeria. IJASSE.
- Onajite, G. O. (2022). Teaching strategies employed by teachers for improving students' learning in business education in secondary schools in Delta State. British Journal of Education.
- Plastina, A. F. (2013) Multimodality in English for specific purposes: Reconceptualizing meaning-making practices. LFE: Revista de Lenguas Para Fines Específicos. doi: 10.892yrPlastina.
- Sankey, M., Birch, D. & Gardiner, M. (2010) Engaging students through multimodal learning environments: The journey continues. Proceedings ascilite Sydney. <http://ascilite.org.au/conferences/sydney10/procs>.

- Mohammed, & Awal-adam (2020) Effect of Multimodal Instructional Strategies on teaching and learning of social studies in senior high schools: A case study in Sagnarigu Municipality DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.10369.07523. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343222173>.
- McKee, L. (2017) Pedagogies of Possibilities: (Re)designing Teacher Professional Learning to Support the Use of Digital Technologies in Multimodal Pedagogies. Electronic Thesis and Dissertation Repository.
- Uchefuna, O. A. (2011). Improving students' performance and attitude in Chemistry through problem-based-solving techniques (PBST). International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development.